

Az alkohol, a drog és a dohányzás hatásai a reprodukciós egészségre és Szexuálisan közvetített betegségek (STI)

The effects of alcohol, drug and smoking on the Reproductive Health and Sexually Transmitted Infections (STI)

Szerkesztők: Prof. Dr. Dékány Imre, Dr. Bitó Tamás, Prof. Dr. Bártfai György

Az MTA Szegedi Akadémiai Bizottság Reprodukciós Egészség Munkabizottsága,
a European Society of Contraception and Reproductive Health és a SZTE Szülészeti és
Nőgyógyászati Klinika közös rendezvénye

Joint meeting of the Reproductive Health Working Group of the Regional Committee of the
Hungarian Academy of Sciences the European Society of Contraception and Reproductive
Health and the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of the University of Szeged

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Absztrakt kötet

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The importance of environmental and bad habit factors (drug, alcohol consumption and smoking habits) in screening of pregnant women with risk for preterm delivery

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Introduction

Preterm delivery is still one of the leading problems in modern obstetrics world wide. It presents important cause of perinatal morbidity and mortality and it is economic burden to health sistem of all countries and especialy poor countries in transtition both in Europe and world wide. It is believed that 6-10% of all pregnancies ends with preterm delivery in countries of western Europe and north America, and participate in 2/3 of cases of perinatal mortality.

Multiple epidemiology studies indicates big influence of: age, socioeconomic status, marital status, maternal antropometric parameters, and also using of alcohol, medications and smoking both before pregnancy and during pregnancy, in increasing of risk for preterm delivery.

Consumation od alcohol during pregnancy can lead to severe malformaitons of fetus considering that alcohol have unobstructed passage through transplacental barrier and has long time of retention in amniotic fluid in degradable form. Also undeveloped excretory system in fetal age as well as slower metabolism contribute to the malformation of fetus.

It is assumed that damaging of the fetus is result of production of free toxic radicals under the influence of undegradable ethanol, which leads to the damaging of cellular enzyme systems and other cellular proteins and lipids, which resultis either in disorder of proliferation and diferentiation of cells leading final to the malformation of fetus or programmed cell death – apoptosis, which results in spontaneous abortions in early period of pregnancy (1. 2, 3, 4).

Eastern Europe area, and especially eastern Balkan presents endemic area in terms of diseases related to the bad nutrition habits, and physical inactivity, such as diabetes melitus, arterial hypertension, obesity, hyperlipidemia, cardiovascular disorders, metabolic syndorome X, and other that also affect the population of women in generative period, which results in complications in pregnancy of all whicah are more stress preterm delivery, preeclampsia, spontaneous abortions and other.

Objective

Aim of this study was to determine which life conditions, bad life habits and pathologies are present in pregnant women, and can these conditions and in which extent can influence the occurrence of preterm delivery.

Methodology

Study was conducted as a prospective study in period between 2010-2013 year in Clinical centre of Vojvodina in Department of obstetrics and gynecology in Novi Sad. Protocol was approved by ethical board of Medical faculty, University of Novi Sad and Ethical board of Clinical centre of Vojvodina (Novi Sad).

Study included 185 pregnant women gestational age between 11. and 14. weeks which are received to the Clinic due to conducting of screening test for chromosomal abnormalities of fetus. All pregnant women confirmed their participation in research by their written consent. Study included all women with average age 18 – 45 years old, with singleton pregnancies, without chromosomal abnormalities of fetus, which are smokers longer than five years and were active smokers during conception. Pregnant women were divided into two groups: control group (healthy pregnant women n=97) and study group (pregnant women with higher risk of occurrence of preterm delivery n=88). Study group include women with history data about alcohol consumption during pregnancy which is determined by Cage protocol, and more than two positive answers were considered enough for inclusion of the women in study group (n=11), than pregnant women with history data of using opiates and other medicaments during pregnancy (n=2), than women which had BMI over 35 with chronic hypertension or just revealed hypertension in pregnancy (n=51), and gestational diabetes (21), or with confirmed bacterial vaginosis and other infections of urogenital tract (n=14). All pregnant women are followed until end of pregnancy with special reference to week of pregnancy completion and delivery mode.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed in statistical package Statistička SPSS (ver.13) for Windows and p values less than 0,05 have been considered as statistically significant. Student t-test and Mann-Whitney test have been used for comparison of variables between groups.

Results

Table 1 shows characteristics of all women included in study: age of pregnant women, BMI index, period of smoking expressed in years, values of systolic and diastolic blood pressure and week of pregnancy completion. Average age of women in study group was statistically significantly higher (0.0046) compared to the control group. Both groups had a same number of smokers: in study group (35,56%) and in control group (35,44%), however period of smoking (values are expressed in years) was statistically significant higher in study group in relation to the control group (p=0,04). Systolic blood pressure was statistically higher in study group (p=0,032).

Average week of ending of pregnancy in study group was statistically significant lower $p=0,023$ than in control group. **Table 1.**

Table 1 Age of pregnant women, BMI, period of smoking expressed in years, arterial blood pressure, week of pregnancy completion (t-test).

	Study group (n=88)	Control group (n=97)	p values
Age	30,04 ± 6,07	27,13 ± 4,98	0,0046
BMI	23,82 ± 3,67	23,50 ± 3,95	0,484
Smoking/years	10,81±4,17	8,14±5,13	0,04
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	122±8,0	107±4,0	0,032
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	81±2,0	80±3,0	0,475
Week of delivery	37,51±3,856	39,47±1,25	0,023

*SC: study group, CG: control group.

Also, statistically higher number of pregnant women of study group lives in urban region 64,44% in regard to the women of control group 35,56% ($p<0,03$). **Figure 1.**

patients followed with preterm delivery, can be added to the group of predictors of preterm delivery.

Literature

1. Goldenberg RL, Goepfert AR, Ramsey PS. Biochemical markers for the prediction of preterm birth. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2005; 192:36-46.
2. Krupa FG, Faltin D, Cecatti JG, Sunita FGC, Souza JP. Predictors of preterm birth. *IJ of Gynaecol and obstet.* 2006; 94:5-11.
3. Goldenberg RL, Goepfert AR, Ramsey PS. Biochemical markers for the prediction of preterm birth. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2005; 192:36-46.
4. Simhan HN, Caritis SN. Prevention of preterm delivery. *N Engl J Med* 2007;357:477–87
5. Murphy D. Epidemiology and environmental factors in preterm labour. *Clin. Obst. and Gyn.* 2007; 21, 773-789.
6. Silva ID, Quevedo LA, Silva RA, Oliveira SS, Pinheiro RT. Association between alcohol abuse during pregnancy and birth weight. *Rev Saúde Pública* 2011;45(5).

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